

EDUCATION OF WOMEN AND SOCIO –ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA**Dr. Monika Mehrotra*, Archana Shukla***Assistant professor Department of Economics Nims university shobha nagar Jaipur Raj.
Ph.d Scholar Department of Economics Nims university shobha nagar Jaipur Raj.**DOI:****KEYWORDS:** Women Education, Social-Issues, civilization, Education for all.**ABSTRACT**

Women's access to education has been recognized as a fundamental right. At the national level, Educating women results in improved productivity, income and economic development, as well as a better quality of life, not ably a heal their and better nourished population. The contribution of female education has been very important. This paper focuses on the importance of women education and highlights its significance for socio economic development. Some recent research on the social and the economic benefits of female education and considers the pathways through which women's schooling leads to social gains. These findings may provide the importance of women's education.

“If you educate a man you educate an individual, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered”. PT. JAWAHARLAL NEHRU

INTRODUCTION

Women education is very important for the proper social and economic development of the country. Both men and women are like two sides of the coin and run equally like. Two wheels of the society so both are important element of the growth and development in the country thus require equal opportunity in the education. If any one of both goes downside, social progress is not possible. For more than 2000 years, from about Bc 300, there was practically no education for women in India. Only a few women of the upper castes and upper classes were given some education at home .But even here there was tremendous social resistance.

Development has been appropriately conceptualized as a process which improves the quality of life of people. Socio economic development of an area depends on the levels of agricultural development and infrastructural facilities available in the area under study. Therefore an attempt has been made to quantify the status of development at block level in respect of agricultural development, infrastructural facilities and over all socio-economic development.

MEANING OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC

Socio-economic development, therefore, is the process of social and economic development in a society. It is measured with indicators such as gross domestic product (GDP), life expectancy, literacy and levels of employment. For better understanding of socio-economic development, we may understand the meaning of social and economic development separately.

Social development is a process which results in the transformation of social institutions in a manner which improves the capacity of the society to fulfill its aspirations.

Status of women in India:-

United Nations has defined the status of women as the “conjunction” of position a women occupies as a worker, student wife, mother ----- of the power and prestige attached to these positions, and of the right and duties she is expected to exercise(UN,1975). In general, women with higher education tend to have a better position. but sometimes education alone cannot be the determinant.

Woman status is high when they contribute substantially to primary substantially to primary subsistence activities. Woman always have secondary status. Educational and health status of women is extremely low in developing countries and in India.

Women education in India has been an urgent need of the new era. We cannot hope for the developed nation without proper education of the women of the country. Women play very important role in the progress of a family; society, and country. In order to make democracy successful in the country Women education is necessary together with the men. Educated women are the real source of happiness in the family, society and country. It is very truly said that educating a man educate a educate whole family and thus whole nation a day.

It is very necessary to highlight on the importance of female education in the country because women are first teacher of their children. Future of the child depends on the love and care of the mother means a woman. Every child get his /her very first lesson through the mother thus it is very important for a mother to educate as only a well-educated mother can shape.

A woman performs the role of many characters throughout her life such as a daughter, sister, wife and mother. Before being involved in any relationship, first she is a free citizen of the independent country and has all rights like man. They have rights to get proper Education to perform better in all areas of life. women education help them to be more independent and empowered in their life. Education help them to grow their mind and status and not be a burden to their parents like past times. Education help them to be well aware of their duties and rights as well as realize their responsibilities to contribute forwards development of the country as same as men do.

THE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL GAINS FROM FEMALE EDUCATION

Equality of the sexes in terms of men and women's command over resources their access to education and health, and in terms of freedom to develop their potential has an intrinsic value in its own right female education increases the value of women's time in economic activities by raising labor productivity and wages. Female education also produces social gains, by improving health, increasing child schooling and reducing fertility.

In India, women achieve for less education that of men. As per the census report 2001, the literacy rate of women in 54.16% and that of men is 65.38%. There has been a sincere effort to improve the education attainment of women by both government and voluntary organizations. The changes in the policies and infrastructural supports on primary, secondary and higher education reflect the initiatives of the government of India towards women education.

Economic efficiency: - If female schooling raises human capital, productivity and economic growth as much male schooling does, then women's disadvantage in education is economically inefficient. Research worldwide shows that, in general the economic benefits from women's education calculated as the economic rate of return to education those from men's education. Thus from the point of view of economic efficiency, the gender gap in education is undesirable. The education industry has two characteristic which make it a prime candidate for a study of efficiency: size and rising costs education represents one of the largest industries in the nation with estimated total direct expenditures of about GDP.

The substantial increase in resource costs, coupled with growing dis-satisfaction with the schools, has surely raised important questions about the Performance of the educational sector. In response economists have increasingly devoted their attentions to studying the internal efficiency of the educational sector and their early efforts suggest a natural bifurcation into camps of optimism.

The way forward: - Although much work has been done to improve the state of education in India we are still a long way off from attaining standards comparable even to other developing nations. India is ranked 109 amongst 128 countries in its education. Index for women.

Although there is much work to be done to enhance education in India particular attention is warranted to women's access to education. The state must play a prominent role in preventing gender stereotyping and segregation in

education, and providing stipends, scholarships, loans, transport facilities guidance to women and their families, especially belonging to the lower and marginalized sections of society below are some recommendations and suggestions for improving access to education for women of the country.

CONCLUSION

Educated women are just on the threshold of transition from tradition to modernity. The women themselves desire that their status and position in society should rise higher. Though a proper climate for such a change is still wanting, yet there have been many structural and statutory innovations for the improvement of their position. The traditional status and role sets of women are breaking up and new role sets based on achievement, independence and equality are gradually coming up.

In this paper I have summarized the findings of recent research showing that social gains from female school in are generally for greater than those from male schooling. These findings have led in recent years, to wide spread recognition of the importance of women's education though the principle still faces challenges from certain quarters. International agencies that provide development assistance to economically less developed countries have come to realize the momentous advantages of expanding girls access to schooling and are now enthusiastically on a key issue like education is welcome indeed. I have also argued the educational per se is not sufficient .It is clear that societies which have achieved universal education are currently extremely deficient socially despite their economic prosperity.

PATHWAYS THROUGH WHICH EDUCATION AFFECTS SOCIAL OUTCOMES

Economists tend to focus on the role of incentives as a way of understanding phenomena. They reason that female education lowers the fertility rate by reducing desired family size, and that this in turn, in because education raises the value of women's economic activities by raising the labor market rewards for going out of the home for work. In other words the opportunity-cost of staying at home for child Bering and rearing increases as women become more educated and so educated women desire smaller families. So women's cash income than men's is spent on child goods. So women's education and the consequent increase in women's income would appear to have particular benefits for child quality.

Education of women improves child health because of the educated mother's greater knowledge of the importance of hygiene and of simple remedies. All this lowers infant mortality, which in turn means that a family does not need to have a large number of children in order to hedge against the possibility of the premature death of some children.

Finally some studies find that mother's education has greater impact on the educational attainment and school achievement of children than father's education. This is plausible given the greater interaction between mother and children in most families since in most countries, fathers are usually the main earners in the household. In this way, education of females contributes more significantly (than the education of males) to increases in human capital productivity and economic growth not only in their own generation but also in the next generation

SOCIO- ECONOMIC STATUS

Socio-economic status (SES) is evaluated as a combination of factors including income level of education and occupation. It is way of looking at how individuals or families fit into society using economic and social measures that have been shown to impact an individual's health and wellbeing (<http://std.about.com>).

Socio-economic status depends on a combination of variables including occupation, education, income, wealth and place of residence. SES is an economic and sociological measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's as family's economic and social position relative to other, based on income education and occupation. When analyzing a family SES the household income earners, education and occupation are examined as well as the combined income versus with an individual when their own attributes are assessed.

Socio-economic status is typically broken into three categories, high SES, middle SES and low SES to describe the three areas a family or an individual may fall into. When placing a family or an individual may fall into when placing a family or individual into one of these. Categories any oral of the three variable (income, education and Occupation) can be assessed.

MAIN FACTORS IN SOCIO –ECONOMIC STATUS

1. Income: - Reference to wages salaries profits, rents and any flow of earnings received. Income an also come in the form of unemployment or workers compensation social security pension's interest of family financial assistance.
2. Education: - Education also plays a role in income. Earning increase with each level of education. The highest degrees, professional and doctoral degrees, make the highest weekly earnings while those with our high school diploma earn less. Education plays a major role in skill sets for acquiring jobs, as well as specific qualities that stratify people with higher SES from lower SES.
3. Occupation:- Occupation prestige as one component of SES encompasses both income and educational all ainment.Occupational status measures social position by describing job characteristics , decision making ability and control and psychological demands of a job occupation is the most difficult factor to measure because so many exist and there are so many competing scales statuses based on inborn characteristics, such as gender are called as cribbed statuses, while statuses that individuals gained through their own efforts are called achieved statuses

GENDER EQUALITY IN EDUCATION: A UNIVERSAL VALUE

Equality between women and men (gendered quality) refers to the equal rights responsibilities and opportunities of women and men and girls a boys.

Equality does not men that women and men rights, responsibilities and opportunities will not depend on whether they are born male or female. Gender equality implies that the interest needs and priorities of both women and men are taken into consideration recognizing the diversity of different groups of women and men gender equality is not a women's issue but should concern and fully engage men as well as women equality between women and men is seen both as a human rights issue and as a precondition for, and indicator of sustainable people centered development. There are four main dimensions of gender equality outlined in the frame work.

1. Equality of access
2. Equality in the learning process
3. Equality of educational outermost and
4. Equality of external results.

Gender equality means males and females have equal opportunities to realize their full human rights and contribute to and benefit from economic social cultural, and politic development parity and equity are the building blacks of equality in education.

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